

SOCIAL TENSION AND SOCIAL PROTESTS AS CONSEQUENCES OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The paper contains a review of classical approaches to the definition of society, social tension, and social movements. Social movements, especially those that take the form of protest, are considered. Possible sources of data used for analyzing social tension and protest activity – results of social surveys and data from social networks. The concept of "society" in classical and modern science is multifaceted. Society is a system of relationships between people built in a certain way, the basis of which is the norms of morality and universal values. Within the framework of Marxist ideology as one of the leading paradigms of the 20th century, society is defined through the joint activity of people. In the research of the British anthropologist Bronislaw Malinowski, society is represented as a system that functions within the framework of activities aimed at individual needs satisfaction. This provokes the development of coordination skills and improved connections between people, which become especially strong during periods of severe shocks. Social tension is a multidimensional concept that reflects, among others, the degree of dissatisfaction of the population with socio-economic conditions of life, while the main "pain points" are a decrease in the standard of living, insufficient housing, labor conflicts, etc. Special attention is paid to the socio-economic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic: job loss, reduced well-being, and inability to lead a previous, habitual lifestyle. Their danger lies in the potential reason for the growth of protest activity.

Keywords: *Society, Social Movements, Social Tension, Pandemic*

1. INTRODUCTION

Any society has a set of characteristics that determine stability or instability in time and space (within territories, on border territories, and in a global sense). One of these characteristics is the presence and intensity of social movements [1]. Social movements arise only in the presence of changes induced by the society itself and its members, and in the extremely negative case they are protests. At the same time, the activity of protest actions increases in the event of complex or potentially conflict situations and leads society out of a state of inertia. The work of Italian sociologists Donatella Della Porte and M. Diani [2, 3] outlines the main features of social movements: common values and solidarity.

2. STAGES OF SOCIAL MOVEMENTS

All social movements go through several stages in their development [4]:

1. Appearance. At this stage, social movements have virtually no organization. The stage of occurrence is rather an expression of public discontent [5]. Possible actions of individuals at this stage: discussions of the situation with friends, complaints to local authorities, and others. The increase in discontent is due to the accumulation of negative information and increasing its coverage in the media. The easiest way to extinguish a growing conflict is at this stage;
2. Overgrowth. The stage of growth is characterized not only by an open manifestation of discontent, but also by its strengthening, as well as attempts to find or "assign" the culprit for the existing problems. According to [5], at this stage riots become apparent and acquire the character of an "epidemic". Mass rallies are held;

3. Bureaucratization. At this stage, social movements not only become controlled from within, but also acquire a development strategy. It is not enough to hold mass rallies alone, and social movements are coordinated with the help of qualified personnel. Requirements for social movements at the stage of bureaucratization – constant mobilization of new members, support for the necessary level of emotional excitement and, most importantly, the presence of coordinators. But these requirements are too high for some protest campaigns. This leads to their attenuation [6];
4. Decline. At the final stage of the existence of social movements, there is a decline in activity, which, however, does not always mean their destruction [7].

Since the 1990s of the twentieth century, research interest in the emergence of new forms of protest and the reasons for the growth of social tension in local territories has increased [8]. According to the results of the analysis of protest activity, the growth of which is caused by the struggle with the introduction of large social and socio-economic projects, these protests are limited in the context of the territory [9]. Each observed case of the most acute social protest is a demonstration of deviant behavior, in this case-a community of protest actions. These actions are aimed at supporting social changes that occur outside of historically and legally established social institutions [10].

3. PROTEST AND ITS DEPENDANCE ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT LEVEL

It is not fair to assume that in economically developed countries the emergence of social movements in the form of protest is less likely than in undeveloped States. Economic stability and the refusal of the population to support radical movements are sometimes cited as reasons. However, recent events in several countries (France – "yellow vests", Spain – the demand for independence of Catalonia, the long-running protests in Hong Kong, and others) show the opposite. The reason is in the system of satisfying the needs of individuals. In developing, poor, and developing countries, basic survival needs are mostly met. The higher the level of socio-economic development of a country, the higher the degree of disunity within society due to the weakening of traditional values and aspirations. That is, in such cases, there is an increase in social imbalance-an anomaly [11]. According to the American sociologist Robert king Merton, members of unstable societies subject to anomie have similar social and personal traits. Thus, they consider themselves incapable of achieving their goals and are convinced that it is impossible to get support from state public institutions, since their leaders are indifferent to the life, opinion and aspirations of ordinary citizens [12]. The existence of serious contradictions between the goals that society sets for individuals and the legal ways to achieve them leads to a few serious consequences. Among them – the growth of social tension and extreme deviant behavior (crime, pogroms, terrorism, extremism, etc.) [13]. Thus, the emergence of social movements as a social phenomenon can be explained by several factors. Among them [14]:

- Economic (poverty, enrichment of a certain group of people against the background of growing differentiation of the population by income);
- Social and socio-demographic (age, gender, profession, etc.);
- Political (commitment to certain political parties and movements);
- Cultural and civilizational (the ability, desire, and desire of the population to actively change the conditions and way of life);
- Ideological (the presence and power of the main ideological direction that strengthens or restrains the growth of protest activity) and others.

There are several classes of social movements. The most radical among them are the revolutionary ones [15]. Their goal is to completely change the existing socio-political system. According to the "theory of revolution" developed by the American sociologist James Davis,

the onset of a state of sharp decline in society, replacing the state of prosperity and recovery, leads to revolutionary movements in society [16]. In other words, the protest is not caused by a lack of resources to meet needs, but by an increase in living requirements and a desire to further improve living conditions. Revolutions are riots in which one political group, which has a large public support, replaces another, which is "at the helm of power" at a time. Public sentiment is what determines the degree of political stability [17]. That is, according to James Davis, dissatisfaction with the financial situation is not a determining factor in the emergence of revolutionary moods. Hence, revolutionary sentiments can be supported by representatives of the poorest segments of the population, as well as by people with sufficient material resources [18]. Thus, the motivation to participate in the chain of successive protests, called the "Arab spring", was formed not only within the framework of perceptions of inequality and poverty, but also in the context of the opportunities available to elites and the population of countries affected by the wave of protest [19].

4. PROTEST RESEARCH AND MODELLING

Currently, one of the main players in the formation and development of social protests is the mass media [20]. News, analytical and informational resources, as well as social networks [21], [22] - a base for strengthening protest activity, fueling interest in existing problems in society and openly discussed. The analysis of protest activity, social movements, and the level of social tension is related not only to analytical analysis of the current situation, but also to working with huge amounts of data [23]. An example of an information and analytical resource that accumulates news notes and other information in the world's media and social networks and provides comprehensive analytical tools is GDELT [24]. The GDELT database, created by Kalev Litaru, contains information about more than two hundred and fifty million events in all countries of the world since 1979. In 2017, another project of Kalev Litaru was presented, a destrometer-a measure of the level of socio-political tension in society [25]. Given the amount of information in the GDELT database and its like, supercomputer capacities are used for calculations. Some technical and methodological aspects of their application are given in [26]. We note several projects in the field of assessing the level of protest activity or revolutionary sentiments using supercomputer technologies:

1. Research performed at the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute (USA), "Social consensus through the influence of committed minorities" ("Social consensus as a result of the influence of a convinced minority in society as a whole") in the study of the probability of regime change in several States. As a result, it is determined that only when the ten percent threshold of the number of supporters of an idea is exceeded, this idea will be dominant [27];
2. Under the leadership of Kalev Leetaru, the Nautilus supercomputer was used to analyze news feed data (more than a hundred million notes were studied in total). The study provides a forecast of increased protest activity in the States affected by the wave of the "Arab spring" [28];
3. The model of social risks implemented in the research Institute of high-tech computer technologies in 2011 at the facilities of the Lomonosov-2 supercomputers (Lomonosov Moscow state University) and Lobachevsky state University [29]. The model calculates a deviation from a pre-defined scenario to determine the depth of social problems. The project developers carry out daily monitoring of social networks about the proliferation of conflict or potential conflict situations. The former may include, for example, support and sympathy for terrorist organizations. The second category is the manifestation of growing discontent among the population in several key areas (for example, tariffs for housing and communal services, fuel costs, inflation, etc.);

4. The system developed to analyze complex social systems and possible responses [30]. In particular, the speed of dissemination of information in social networks and news that can potentially affect the growth of social tension is assessed. In addition, this model is used to assess the life cycle, stages of development and extinction of financial systems and criminal structures.

In addition to aggregated data from the media, the results of sociological surveys of the population are used to assess potentially "explosive" situations and conflicts. Thus, when analyzing the causes and consequences of the already mentioned chain of Arab spring protests, the state of the problem of illegal immigration of the population of the Middle East and North Africa to Europe, and other topical issues, the results of social monitoring by Arab Barometer and Eurobarometer, respectively, were used. The basis for the emergence of protest movements is a whole set of factors, including social, economic, political, and psychological aspects of human and social life. The COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic was a trigger that triggered not only an increase in panic over the pandemic spread of a previously unknown disease. The restrictive measures taken to implement in most countries of the world, the temporary suspension of international trade and the suspension of many enterprises, and, as a result, the decline in industrial energy consumption, combined with a sharp drop in the price of oil – these and other reasons have become factors that have induced crisis phenomena in the world economy, e.g. inflation growth and rising unemployment. Decrease in the purchasing power of income combined with a decrease in the amount of disposable income on the hands of the population, etc. These and other issues have the potential to have a large-scale protest potential that can involve many individuals in the movement.

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